

1 A knowledge graph-based framework to automate the
2 generation of building energy models using geometric relation
3 checking and HVAC topology establishment

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6 **Abstract**

7 Building Energy Models (BEM) are widely utilized throughout all stages of a build-
8 ing’s lifecycle to understand and enhance energy usage. However, creating these mod-
9 els demands significant effort, particularly for larger buildings or those with complex
10 HVAC systems. While a substantial amount of information can be extracted from
11 Building Information Models (BIM) — which are increasingly accessible and provide
12 necessary data for geometric and HVAC contexts — this information is not readily
13 usable in setting up BEM and typically requires manual translation. To address this
14 challenge, this paper introduces a BIM-to-BEM (BIM2BEM) framework that focuses
15 on automating the generation of HVAC parts of BEM models from BIM data. Core
16 to the methodology is the extraction of HVAC system topologies from the BIM model
17 and the creation of a knowledge graph with the HVAC topology. The topology trans-
18 formation unfolds in three key stages: first, a geometry-induced knowledge graph is
19 established by examining the geometric relationships among HVAC elements; second,
20 this graph is converted into an informative HVAC topology with enhanced properties
21 from additional data sources; and finally, the informative topology is simplified into a
22 BEM-oriented HVAC topology compliant with BEM platforms such as EnergyPlus.
23 A case study of a large university building with a complex HVAC system showcases
24 that the proposed framework achieves automatic and precise generation of building
25 performance simulation models. The model’s predictions are then validated against
26 actual measurements from the building.

27 *Keywords:* Building digital twins; BIM2BEM; Ontology; HVAC topology;
28 Geometric relation checking

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1. Introduction

Accurate representation of Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning (HVAC) systems is essential for energy modelling throughout the building lifecycle and for digital twin applications that support building operational management [1]. While the importance of HVAC topology representation is widely acknowledged, manual instantiating remains a significant challenge. Automating the extraction of HVAC topology information can greatly enhance its applicability across design and operational domains [2]. Building Information Modelling (BIM), which provides detailed and comprehensive building and HVAC data, can support the generation of HVAC topology that aligns with the input requirements of Building Energy Models (BEM). To fully exploit this potential within the BIM-to-BEM (BIM2BEM) process, a seamless transformation framework is required, with an emphasis on integrating HVAC data from BIM into the BEM context. This framework is underpinned by two critical sub-processes: (a) the automated extraction of HVAC topology from BIM data and (b) the subsequent mapping of this topology into a specific BEM context. Hence, the present study proposes a knowledge graph-based approach, focusing on HVAC systems, which employs geometric relation-checking techniques to automate the establishment of HVAC topology. The relevant information within this topology is then effectively transferred into the geometric BEM model, resulting in a simulation-ready model with a fully detailed HVAC configuration.

1.1. Literature review

Early work by Bazjanac et al. [3], showcased the potential but also challenges of BIM2BEM methods. This potential is realised through BIM's parametric modelling capabilities and interoperability standards, which make it an effective data source for building energy models [4]. BIM provides a detailed and accurate representation of architectural and HVAC information, including geometric data, system connections, and specific properties, making it a reliable foundation for performance simulations [5]. Unlike other data sources, a BEM derived from BIM preserves the intricate details of the building design, thereby minimising human assumptions and biases. Moreover, simulation uncertainties often stem from imperfections and insuf-

1 efficient information in data sources—issues that BIM effectively resolves by providing
2 a reliable and comprehensive representation of the building [6].

3 The process of generating a BEM from BIM has been the subject of extensive
4 research, covering aspects of the transformation process and focused on approaches
5 for multi-domain data integration covering a wide range of domains such as build-
6 ing geometry, building envelopes, energy systems, occupant behaviour, and control
7 strategies. The transfer of building geometry information is a core area of interest
8 within this domain, attracting significant research into efficient methodologies and
9 effective data sources. Many geometry-related algorithms have been developed to
10 tackle the challenge of extracting the second-level space boundary (2LSB) topology
11 from BIM models, which is essential for accurately creating building geometry mod-
12 els for performance simulations [7, 8, 9, 10]. In exchanging information from BIM
13 to energy-modelling tools, two data formats are frequently used: the Green Building
14 XML schema (gbXML) and Industry Foundation Classes (IFC). The stated pur-
15 pose of gbXML is to be an interoperable data format for energy-related information
16 exchanges and is a widely adopted exchange scheme for building geometry descrip-
17 tions, as reported by Yang et al. [11]. One of the benefits of gbXML is its ability
18 to minimise the manual effort involved in restructuring building models for energy
19 modelling, thereby streamlining the handling of input data. However, a persistent
20 challenge remains in extracting the necessary information for data exchange in either
21 format (gbXML or IFC). Tools that can process geometric data from BIM models
22 to extract second-level space boundaries (2LSB) are indispensable, regardless of the
23 container format used. Delgado et al. [12] utilized Revit to export gbXML from BIM
24 data captured by drones, which was then imported into a streamlined BIM2BEM
25 workflow for modelling a single-family wooden house in Portugal. Another Revit-
26 based workflow considering gbXML as the BIM input data format was proposed by
27 Elnabawi [13], who emphasised that the lack of standardisation results in variations
28 between modellers and may cause delays in its application. Furthermore, the IFC
29 schema is a comprehensive BIM data standard encompassing a broad range of build-
30 ing data and managing complex, multidisciplinary information, making it highly
31 versatile for collaboration throughout the building lifecycle. Its broad support by

1 BIM tools and regular updates to align with industry needs encourage scholars to
2 explore its integration into BIM2BEM workflows. Ramaji et al. [14] investigated
3 the study on IFC-based BIM2BEM workflow to translate the open BIM standards
4 into OpenStudio data format, concentrating on architectural information conver-
5 sion. Chen et al. [15] proposed a BIM2BEM toolkit, AutoBPS-BIM, combined with
6 a chiller optimisation module to evaluate energy loads, demonstrating the potential
7 for extending the BIM2BEM process. Giannakis et al. [16] proposed an automatic
8 BIM2BEM workflow integrating a series of tools, including the Revit IFC Exporter,
9 Common Boundary Intersection Projection (CBIP) tool, and SimModel XML tool,
10 to generate an EnergyPlus Input Data File (IDF) with precise building geometric
11 configurations. Moreover, the interoperability of building geometry and envelope
12 information between gbXML and IFC was also investigated by Kamel et al. [17],
13 demonstrating its potential to enhance BIM2BEM transformation. Among the vari-
14 ous types of building information, research on geometric data within the BIM2BEM
15 domain is relatively advanced, with several effective workflows already established
16 that provide proof of concept. However, their scalability remains in question, as
17 many fail to perform effectively in practice. Hence, studies recently have increas-
18 ingly focused on generating reliable BEM geometric models from imperfect BIM
19 sources, as well as extending these workflows to other information types, such as
20 building envelopes and mechanical systems.

21 Another important domain in the transformation is the handling of building sys-
22 tems, such as HVAC, where accurate transformation leads to more realistic building
23 simulation models with detailed settings for active components. Pinheiro et al. [18]
24 emphasized that the IFC Model View Definition (MVD) standardizes information
25 exchange within specific domains, including HVAC systems, thereby streamlining
26 BEM development and reducing modelling time, which can further support a semi-
27 automatic BIM2BEM workflow. Autodesk Insight, a tool integrated with Revit,
28 facilitates building performance simulation within the BIM2BEM process by incor-
29 porating HVAC settings, as reported by Gonzalez et al. [19]. EnergyPlus, the "gold
30 standard" for whole building simulation, excels in modelling energy use, HVAC sys-
31 tems, and thermal performance, making it ideal as the simulation engine for the

1 BIM2BEM process. Barone et al. [20] generated a preliminary building energy model
2 for EnergyPlus using an automated BIM-to-gbXML-to-OpenStudio import routine,
3 in which the HVAC system was modelled manually using the OpenStudio Applica-
4 tion GUI. Li et al. [21] developed an automatic transformation approach to convert
5 HVAC information from IFC data to OpenStudio by leveraging a data-driven reverse
6 engineering algorithm. Their approach’s effectiveness and precision were showcased
7 through a case study of an office building. Besides using EnergyPlus as the sim-
8 ulation engine, Modelica provides flexible, component-based modelling of complex
9 building systems, making it another viable option to support dynamic simulation
10 in the BIM2BEM process. Kim et al. [22] developed a Modelica library for BIM-
11 based building simulation via an Object-oriented physical modelling (OOPM) ap-
12 proach. They investigated the system interface between BIM and BEM, concentrat-
13 ing on component-level simulation. Sayegh et al. [23] presented a semi-automated
14 BIM2BEM workflow using Modelica and BuildingSysPro, providing templates for
15 HVAC settings. They introduced a two-storey building as the case study to high-
16 light the manual intervention required to detect and correct errors in BIM. IDA
17 Indoor Climate and Energy (IDA ICE) was also used by Hosamo et al. [24]. Based
18 on the above studies, whole-building simulation models require specific inputs and
19 syntax. Despite these differences, certain key information areas must be addressed in
20 all models. Tools like EnergyPlus include the geometric context of zone boundaries,
21 as well as HVAC system topology. Meanwhile, the need for higher-quality BIM data
22 has increased as the accuracy of transforming geometric and HVAC data improves.
23 Low-quality BIM data can significantly hinder the automation of the BIM2BEM pro-
24 cess, often requiring manual adjustments that reduce both efficiency and scalability.

25 While stating and meeting the information and exchange requirements is essen-
26 tial, the data structure adopted to represent relevant information is also important.
27 If taking as an example the HVAC topology, which is of interest, using a data for-
28 mat like gbXML is an option. Yet, this information might also be useful in other
29 analysis contexts, such as operation and maintenance or Digital Twins. To support
30 information reuse across domains and specific applications, it is useful to select an
31 ontology as a structured framework for representing and organizing relevant knowl-

1 edge representation. Such an approach is interesting, focusing on the core concepts,
2 relationships, and entities rather than requirements linked to a specific information
3 exchange. By separating knowledge extraction — such as Building or HVAC system
4 topologies — from how this information will be used, a clearer separation of concerns
5 is achieved. Such structures have improved data interoperability and ensured seam-
6 less interaction across multiple domains, including energy performance and spatial
7 analysis [25].

8 There are several ontologies used in the building domain [26], with extensive dis-
9 cussions on their potential applications. Of special interest for HVAC systems are
10 the Brick Schema [27], Flow Systems Ontology (FSO) [28], and TUBES System On-
11 tology (TSO) [29]. FSO and TSO are compatible with BIM data, focusing on energy
12 and mass exchange in building system models at varying levels of granularity. At the
13 same time, Brick provides a more general framework for standardizing building as-
14 sets. Wu et al. [30] extended Brick to facilitate automatic building energy modelling
15 using a rule-based reasoning method for thermal zoning. Their work concentrated on
16 the automatic generation of building geometry yet with a simple hypothetical HVAC
17 system. Fjerbæk et al. [31] automated Modelica-based simulations of heating systems
18 using FSO to provide detailed representations of individual components and struc-
19 tural information of the heating system. They noted that applying this approach to
20 larger, more complex systems would reveal outcomes that regular practitioners find
21 difficult to quantify. These studies demonstrated the capacity of ontological frame-
22 works to structure and integrate building data for performance simulations, facili-
23 tating more detailed and accurate model configurations [32]. Ontologies streamline
24 data integration by addressing the challenge of managing heterogeneous data, offer-
25 ing a solution to improve the reliability and precision of building energy simulations,
26 especially for complex buildings with intricate HVAC systems.

27 In general, current studies in the BIM2BEM context focus on investigating the
28 feasibility and applying their approaches to small-scale buildings with simple energy
29 systems or hypothetical configurations rather than large-scale buildings with complex
30 and diverse HVAC systems. The main challenges may lie in handling heterogeneous
31 data and managing imperfect input BIM data, often leading to incomplete HVAC

1 and 2LSB topologies with unexpected errors. While these efforts have achieved some
2 automation, issues like biased information transfer and poor input data quality still
3 necessitate considerable manual modelling work or corrections. Building ontologies
4 and semantic web technologies to structure and harmonise data offer an effective
5 representation of complex information domains and are more flexible compared to
6 standard BIM-based approaches; this flexibility makes such approaches interesting
7 in such problems.

8 *1.2. Motivation and contribution*

9 As previously mentioned, current BIM2BEM transformation methods depend on
10 high-quality BIM models that can be validated through checking tools. However, in
11 practice, BIM models are often developed for design coordination and collaboration
12 rather than specifically tailored for energy modelling with a focus on HVAC systems.
13 Most available BIM data do not meet the stringent requirements for complex Extract,
14 Transform, and Load (ETL) processes needed to generate accurate building simula-
15 tion models. Therefore, for BIM2BEM workflows to be effective, the transformation
16 processes must be capable of handling BIM models with moderate inaccuracies and
17 design errors. This is particularly important for HVAC systems, where the topology
18 of component interconnections, even with some imperfections, is often sufficient to
19 generate a reliable and accurate BEM for performance simulation.

20 Hence, this study proposes a framework that integrates advanced techniques to
21 effectively extract HVAC information from BIM models with design errors and lever-
22 ages semantic web technologies to establish an HVAC topology that accurately re-
23 flects the real-world system. Then, the framework explores a method for generating
24 BEM by mapping the HVAC topology to EnergyPlus objects. The framework is
25 applied to a newly constructed building with complex HVAC systems to validate its
26 effectiveness and feasibility. The main contributions of this are: (1) From a scientific
27 perspective, the proposed framework efficiently generates reliable, simulation-ready
28 building models with HVAC configurations that accurately mirror real-world sys-
29 tems, even when the input data contains errors; (2) From a practical perspective,
30 the knowledge graph-based techniques introduced in this study facilitate the robust

1 and efficient integration of heterogeneous data, acting as an intermediary between
 2 multi-domain data sources and building performance simulations.

3 The subsequent sections of the paper offer a more detailed explanation of the
 4 proposed approach: Section 2 presents the framework and its key stages, followed
 5 by Section 3, which offers an overview of the case study and the available data.
 6 Section 4 then delves into the results and discusses effectiveness and limitations.
 7 Finally, Section 5 summarize the study’s findings and propose avenues for future
 8 research.

9 2. Methodology

Figure 1: The proposed framework of this study.

10 The proposed methodology for automating BIM2BEM, focusing on HVAC infor-
 11 mation, comprises four key stages, as illustrated in Figure 1.

- 12 (1) **Geometric relation check:** In this stage, one or more BIM models containing
 13 the geometric information for Architectural (ARC) and Mechanical, Electrical,
 14 and Plumbing (MEP) elements are exported in IFC format. A seamless work-
 15 flow, based on the BIM context and a Geometric Relation Checker (GRC) tool,

1 identifies the geometric relations among MEP and ARC elements. A pairwise
2 checking process is then conducted to obtain the geometric relations of each
3 pair in the MEP-IFC file and between terminals in the MEP-IFC file and spaces
4 in the ARC-IFC file.

5 (2) **Knowledge graph generation:** In this stage, a geometry-induced knowledge
6 graph for the HVAC domain is generated according to the geometric checking
7 results obtained from step (1). This work then generates knowledge graphs
8 following the Brick Schema for water loops and air loops, which describe the
9 connections among HVAC elements and the relationships between terminal
10 units and spaces.

11 (3) **BEM-oriented HVAC topology establishment:** In this stage, a path-
12 finding algorithm is introduced to generate an informative HVAC topology to
13 unlock the links among terminal units, Air Handling Units (AHUs), Mechanical
14 Ventilation with Heat Recovery (MVHR), Fan Coil Units (FCUs), and water
15 pumps. The entities referring to pipe segments, duct segments, fittings, and
16 accessory devices are bypassed. Meanwhile, the device inventory is introduced
17 to enrich the informative HVAC topology with device performance properties.
18 Then, a set of rules is proposed to simplify the informative HVAC topology
19 into a BEM-oriented one conforming to the building performance simulation
20 data requirements.

21 (4) **Building energy modelling:** In the final stage, a mapping approach is de-
22 veloped to bridge the gap between BEM-oriented HVAC topology and building
23 performance simulation. This mapping approach automatically generates an
24 EnergyPlus model by combining the topology from step (3), the building's
25 BEM geometric content and other data sources. e.g., weather, schedule, and
26 control strategy. Furthermore, a building performance simulation is conducted
27 to evaluate the current design of the HVAC system in terms of indoor environ-
28 ment and energy consumption.

29 The following four subsections detail each stage of the proposed framework.

1 2.1. Stage 1: Geometric relation check

2 This initial stage aims to generate geometric relation pairs among the geometric
3 solid representations of the building’s MEP elements and space volume geometries.
4 These relations will be used to identify semantic (non-geometric) relations among
5 these elements at a later stage. Three additional subprocesses are involved in this
6 stage, as analysed next.

7 2.1.1. Geometric information extraction

8 IFC, an open standard data model used in BIM, is adopted in this approach
9 to describe, share, and exchange construction and facility management information.
10 Developed by buildingSMART International, IFC serves as a neutral format, en-
11 abling interoperability between various software platforms in architecture, engineer-
12 ing, construction, and operations [33]. Different IFC standard versions have varied
13 in their support for MEP systems. IFC2x3 provided only basic support for HVAC,
14 while IFC4 significantly expanded and restructured this domain, introducing more
15 detailed entity types and a wider range of property sets essential for BIM2BEM
16 workflows. IFC4.3 offers further refinements, but as it is a recent release, widespread
17 tool support is still pending. Therefore, this study focuses on IFC4 and its updates,
18 like IFC4 ADD2 TC1 (ISO 16739-1:2018), which are widely supported by existing
19 tools.

20 Given the IFC4 model, information is extracted from relevant entities within
21 the `IfcHvacDomain`, typically including subtypes of `IfcDistributionFlowElement`.
22 These encompass energy conversion devices (`IfcEnergyConversionDevice`), duct or
23 pipe segments, fittings, terminals, flow-moving devices such as fans or pumps, and
24 flow control elements like valves, dampers, and air terminal boxes.

25 Figure 2 shows the data manipulation diagram of the GRC tool used in this
26 work to check the geometric relationship between elements in BIM models. The IFC
27 Geometry Exporter [34], a component integrated into the cloud platform, was used
28 to derive geometric representations of the specified elements. It extracts the specific
29 shape representation (`IfcShapeRepresentation`) from the IFC files and organizes
30 the geometric information into a hierarchical tree-structured format in XML files.

1 These generated XML files then serve as input for the GRC tool to detect geometric
 2 relationships between pairs of elements. With no prior information available on these
 3 relationships, the GRC tool accelerates the process by first applying Axis-Aligned
 4 Bounding Boxes (AABB) for an initial check, followed by a more detailed analysis.
 5 As AABB requires only a few multiplications and is significantly faster than full
 6 clash detection, it is feasible to evaluate all possible pairs, with a complexity of
 7 $O(n^2)$. As a result, an OBJ file and an XML file are outputted, encapsulating the
 8 geometric relationships needed for further analysis. The GRC tool is currently under
 9 development and not yet available for public use. Following sufficient beta testing, it
 10 will be released as part of a tool bundle, including a Graphical User Interface (GUI)
 11 that allows users to visually verify the detected geometric relationships.

Figure 2: Diagram of the transfer process from IFC to XML, followed by loading into the GRC tool.

12 *2.1.2. Geometric relationship among entities*

13 Although relationships `IfcRelConnectsPorts` and `IfcRelConnectsPortToElement`
 14 describe the connection between the elements in MEP files, some of these connec-
 15 tions may not be explicitly modelled, and the relationship would be missing. This
 16 might not be important for many uses of the BIM model, but if there is a need to
 17 identify connectivity between flow segments, then this information is crucial. One

1 approach is to ask the modeller to model these port connections, but this might not
2 be practical or feasible. To overcome these issues, this work proposes a workflow to
3 address these missing connections. This workflow uses three types of geometric rela-
4 tions that reveal other non-geometric connections between pairs of elements. These
5 relations can be classified as adjacency, clash, and containment. Figure 3 illustrates
6 these geometric relations using conceptual and graphical representations, with more
7 details provided below.

8 **Adjacency:** An adjacency relation between two solids exists when the boundary
9 representation of one solid has surfaces lying within the same plane and intersect-
10 ing with surfaces of the other solid’s boundary representation. Part 1 of Figure 3
11 illustrates the adjacency between two elements. This adjacency occurs in pairs
12 of ducts, especially rectangular-shaped ones, as illustrated in the bottom image
13 of part 1 of Figure 3. Unlike other geometric relations, adjacency detection uses
14 a threshold value to determine the allowable distance between the intersecting
15 surface planes. The adjacency will not be detected if the distance between these
16 planes exceeds this threshold value. The adjacency relation is used to identify
17 connectivity between MEP elements.

18 **Clash:** A clash relation between two solids exists when surfaces or portions of
19 surfaces of the boundary representation of one solid are fully contained within
20 the solid volume of the other. Part 2 of Figure 3, illustrates the clash relation
21 between two elements. This relation is detected among MEP element pairs and
22 space volumes, such as between spaces and terminal units, terminal units and
23 ducts/pipes, ducts and ducts, pipes and pipes, and ducts/pipes and systems.
24 Clash occurrences offer valuable insights related to MEP element connectivity,
25 especially when these connectivity relations in the BIM context are missing.

26 **Containment:** A containment relation between two solids occurs when the sur-
27 faces of one solid’s boundary representation are entirely within the volume of the
28 other. This relation establishes links between spatial entities and terminal units,
29 precisely positioning HVAC terminal units within a building’s spatial structure.
30 This relationship ensures that air terminal units, like diffusers, are fully contained
31 within the building space, as illustrated in part 3 of Figure 3.

	① Adjacency	② Clash	③ Containment
Conceptual			
Graphical			
Geometric relation: Adjacency / Clash / Containment → Semantic relation: Connectivity / Containment			

Figure 3: Conceptual and graphical illustration of geometric relationships, including adjacency, clash, and containment.

1 As analysed next, the above relations induce non-geometric semantic relations
2 among MEP and building space entities.

3 *2.1.3. Geometric relationship check workflow*

4 This workflow is designed to discover all current or potential connections among
5 the MEP entities. It comprises three stages, displayed in Figure 4. First, this work-
6 flow identifies all explicitly modelled connections (designated by `IfcRelConnectsPorts`
7 and `IfcRelConnectsPortToElement`) and compiles a list of connected element pairs.
8 Subsequently, the GRC tool is utilized to uncover additional geometric relationships
9 among these element pairs. The GRC tool can also flag elements with geometric
10 surface errors, which cannot pass through certain geometric relation checks, thus
11 directing them to the Oriented Bounding Boxes (OBB) [35] checking process in the
12 third stage. Additionally, elements with planar geometric representations, such as
13 duct end caps, which lack volume and cannot be handled by the GRC tool, are also
14 routed to the third stage. Ultimately, all linked element pairs from each stage are
15 merged into a consolidated list of linked pairs, maximizing the extraction of connec-
16 tions from MEP-IFC files.

Figure 4: The proposed geometric relationship check workflow with three stages.

2.2. Stage 2: Knowledge graph generation

This stage aims to create an instance of a knowledge graph of HVAC components and related topological information using available information from the BIM model. The proposed approach uses available modelled information and geometric relationship checking to be resilient to potential modelling issues and errors in the BIM model. The resulting knowledge graph captures the HVAC components and their connectivity and can also be useful for the BIM2BEM framework.

2.2.1. Ontology and geometry-induced knowledge graph

Using multiple ontologies concurrently to represent building information is generally more efficient than creating a customised ontology for each project or designing a single comprehensive ontology to encompass all knowledge domains. Integrating multiple ontologies enables the development of a robust digital representation, potentially incorporating one or more knowledge graphs to accurately reflect the building's information [36, 37]. Specifically, in this study, Brick Ontology, developed by the Brick Consortium, is introduced to represent HVAC components, building spaces, and representation of HVAC systems' topology. Brick provides a consistent vocabulary to describe all MEP-related and architectural elements and their

1 interconnections, facilitating the integration of diverse data sources and enabling
2 interoperability across different systems. Additionally, an ETL tool, namely Knowl-
3 edge Graph Generator [38], was employed to facilitate the transformation of HVAC
4 elements from IFC files into corresponding entities within the knowledge graph.

5 Within the Brick framework, the `brick:HVAC` abstract class provides seman-
6 tic descriptions for various components of HVAC systems, covering a wide range
7 of elements from subsystems (e.g., `brick:AHU`, `brick:FCU`, and `brick:Chiller`)
8 to terminal units (`brick:Air_Diffuser`), pumps (`brick:Water_Pump`), VAV boxes
9 (`brick:VAV`), radiators (`brick:Radiator`) among others. In addition to the HVAC
10 class, `brick:Space` and `brick:Room` classes are essential for describing the spaces
11 and rooms within buildings. Since Brick lacks a fully corresponding relationship to
12 precisely represent the direction-agnostic geometric connections obtained from the
13 previous subsection, `brick:isAssociatedWith` (other custom relationships are also
14 applicable) is utilised to enrich the geometry-induced knowledge graph that will sub-
15 sequently be transformed into an HVAC topology. To avoid name duplication, the
16 IFC global unique identifier (GUID) can be transferred into the knowledge graph,
17 either to name the entity or to be stored as a property of the entity.

18 *2.2.2. Error detection and knowledge graph generation*

19 While the geometric relation-checking workflow can extract most connections,
20 some may still be absent due to the data quality of the inputted IFC file. Addressing
21 these issues in this stage is crucial to ensure the accuracy of the generated HVAC
22 topology in subsequent stages. This study proposes a set of rules to identify poten-
23 tial issues in establishing connections between entities, ensuring the completeness of
24 knowledge graphs. These rules are designed to cover most entities within the HVAC
25 domain. For instance, an error will be flagged if a pipe or duct segment entity has
26 fewer than two linked entities. This ruleset is detailed in Table 1.

27 Based on these rules, entities with issues are identified and displayed in a BIM-
28 viewing platform for verification purposes. Users can then manually address the
29 problematic entities by supplementing missing connections or removing non-existent
30 ones in the graph, thereby enabling the creation of a complete graph.

Table 1: Geometry-induced knowledge graph issue ruleset.

Item A	Relation/Property	Item B
Pipe segment	< 2 linked entities	-
Duct segment	< 2 linked entities	-
Duct fitting	< 2 linked entities	-
Pipe fitting	< 2 linked entities	-
Tee pipe	< 3 linked entities	-
Pipe segment	linked to	Duct segment
Duct segment	linked to	Pipe segment
Air diffuser	not linked to	Duct segment
Air Handling Unit (AHU)	not linked to	Non-space entity
Fan Coil Unit (FCU)	not linked to	Pipe segment
Air diffuser	not linked to	Space entity
Air diffuser	linked to	> 1 space entities
Terminal unit	not linked to	Space entity
Terminal unit	linked to	> 1 space entities

1 *2.3. Stage 3: BEM-oriented HVAC topology establishment*

2 This stage establishes a BEM-oriented HVAC topology from the HVAC system’s
 3 geometry-induced knowledge graph. Obtaining the informative HVAC topology is
 4 essential initially, as detailed in the subsequent subsection.

5 *2.3.1. Informative HVAC topology generation*

6 Path-finding algorithms, e.g., depth-first search, can achieve the logical link be-
 7 tween any two entities via specific relationship (predicate) checks, offering greater
 8 flexibility and efficiency than simple queries when handling customized constraints
 9 in complex graphs [39]. Using this capability, these methods can be introduced to
 10 establish logical links between air terminals and systems (including FCUs, AHUs,
 11 and MVHRs), radiators/FCUs/AHUs and pumps/Heat Interface Units (HIUs), and
 12 other critical, logical links between different HVAC equipment. Additionally, the
 13 Variable Air Volume (VAV) box can be identified in the path-finding process, and

1 some entities can be designated as inaccessible to avoid achieving unreasonable links.
2 It is better to apply the path-finding process within the water- and air-loops by split-
3 ting the generated HVAC graph into separate water- and air-loop sub-graphs. In this
4 way, a significant reduction of computing resource requirements can be achieved.

5 Initially, the `brick:isAssociatedWith` relation is used to represent the detected
6 geometric relations of the second stage that refer to semantic connections of HVAC
7 elements. Regarding space entities, the `brick:isLocationOf` is introduced to indi-
8 cate where the assets (e.g., terminal units and systems) are situated. To add the
9 notion of direction, the `brick:feeds` is used to indicate the directional links between
10 AHUs/MVHRs/FCUs and air terminals in air loops. In water loops, the same re-
11 lation can be used to describe the direction of the water supply. In the case study
12 of this work, the airflow direction is determined according to the air terminals' asset
13 labels, in which there is a special string to indicate whether the label refers to an air
14 supply terminal or an air return terminal. The schematic diagram in Figure 5, illus-
15 trates how the informative HVAC topology is generated from the geometry-induced
16 knowledge graph.

17 The outlined approach proves effective in generating an informative HVAC topol-
18 ogy. However, essential data for building energy modelling, including capacity, ef-
19 ficiency, and control strategy, may be lacking in MEP-BIM models below Level Of
20 Development 400 (LOD400). To address this, the study establishes an equipment
21 inventory based on manuals provided by the estate team, encompassing all assets in
22 the HVAC topology. This inventory is then integrated to enrich the topology with
23 equipment performance data. Additionally, room temperature control strategies can
24 be obtained from building management system operation manuals supplied by the
25 estate team.

26 Finally, ensuring the correctness and completeness of the generated informative
27 HVAC topology is essential. Considering that a few subtle logical errors might origi-
28 nate from the BIM inference, this work introduces an additional data quality checking
29 rule set of the generated informative HVAC topology. Potential issues are displayed
30 in the following Table 2. Given that MVHR is not explicitly included in the Brick
31 Ontology, this work utilises the Dedicated Outdoor Air System (DOAS) class as a

Figure 5: Schematic diagram of generating informative HVAC topology based on the path-finding process.

- 1 representation. EnergyPlus also offers a module for modelling DOAS, which can be
- 2 customised to closely resemble MVHR.

Table 2: Informative HVAC topology issue ruleset.

Item A	Relation/Property	Item B
Air terminal	> 1 linked entities	VAV/AHU/DOAS/FCU
Air terminal	not linked entities	-
FCU	not linked to	Water pump entity
AHU	not linked to	Water pump entity
Radiator	not linked to	Hot water pump entity
Water pump	not linked to	Supply-side entity

- 3 The above rules are applied to detect errors in the informative HVAC topology

1 only. Although the path-finding process can also infer some missing links between the
2 above entities, it would be preferable to fix the errors manually through validation
3 against the design drawings or other data sources.

4 *2.3.2. BEM-oriented HVAC topology establishment*

5 Given the introduction of a newly constructed building equipped with complex
6 HVAC systems featuring diverse energy technologies, EnergyPlus has been chosen
7 as the platform for building performance simulation. To align with EnergyPlus's
8 programming syntax, a BEM-oriented HVAC topology is developed by simplifying
9 the detailed HVAC topology, placing emphasis on zone- and space-level granularity.
10 Thus, this study presents a straightforward and effective method for transforming
11 the informative HVAC topology into its BEM-oriented counterpart, as illustrated in
12 Figure 6. The method can be summarized into four parts, outlined as follows:

13 **Space and FCU/VAV bridging:** In the informative HVAC topology, VAV
14 boxes and FCUs are not directly connected to individual spaces; instead, the
15 connection is made through intermediary components, such as air terminals (e.g.,
16 diffusers and grilles). To adapt these connections into usable links within a zone-
17 level BEM-oriented HVAC topology, certain scenarios require the creation of di-
18 rect links between air terminals and VAV/FCU, as depicted in Part A of Figure 6.
19 However, in some cases, air terminals cannot be bypassed, especially when they
20 are directly linked to AHUs or MVHRs, or when they are interconnected with
21 FCUs and MVHRs in series (this will be addressed by a decoupling method de-
22 scribed below).

23 **Terminal units merging at space level:** Generally, terminal units within
24 a single space are typically supplied by the same system according to design
25 conventions. Additionally, for economic reasons and air distribution in ductwork,
26 the terminal units in the same space usually have similar performance [40]. As a
27 result, it is practical to consolidate similar units into a single hypothetical terminal
28 unit with a capacity equal to the combined capacities of the individual units. It is
29 important to note that this approach can only be applied to air terminals serving
30 the same space and supplied by the same source (AHU/MVHR). This method

1 not only complies with the modelling rules of widely used pre-processing tools
2 such as Eppy (via HVACTemplate) and OpenStudio but is also well-suited for
3 modelling a large building equipped with hundreds of diffusers. The schematic
4 diagram is depicted in Part B of Figure 6.

5 **Hot/chilled water-loop construction:** Given the simulation platform’s dic-
6 tionary, it’s essential to introduce a distinct entity for representing water loops.
7 Within the introduced overall framework, all equipment associated with a spe-
8 cific water loop, such as pumps, buffer vessels, valves, and degassing units, are
9 replaced by a generated `brick:Water Loop` class entity. Subsequently, connec-
10 tions are established between these water-loop entities and terminal units or other
11 system entities, e.g., AHUs. This process is illustrated in Part C of Figure 6.

12 **FCU and MVHR decoupling:** As the connections between FCU and MVHR
13 are not directly predefined in the simulation platform’s dictionary, this study
14 introduces a decoupling technique to transform the FCU-MVHR connections from
15 series to parallel feeding the same space. The approach involves relocating the air
16 mixing point from the front of the FCU to the back. Part D of Figure 6 illustrates
17 an example of decoupling the merged FCU-MVHR terminal units.

18 *2.4. Stage 4: Building energy modelling*

19 This study presents an automated framework for creating a BEM model by inte-
20 grating data from BIM and other sources into an HVAC topology. The simulations
21 are conducted using EnergyPlus, which requires an IDF file (BEM model) contain-
22 ing comprehensive descriptions of building geometry, material properties, equipment
23 details, system definitions, climatic conditions, and other simulation parameters.
24 Through the simulation process, a thorough evaluation of building performance re-
25 garding energy usage, indoor comfort levels, and environmental effects can be at-
26 tained.

27 Regarding the IDF file structure, the BEM model can be segmented into two
28 components: the geometrical module and the non-geometrical module. The geomet-
29 rical module within IDF files encompasses the physical characteristics and layout of
30 the building. It includes detailed specifications regarding building geometry, such

Figure 6: Schematic diagram of the methods to transform informative HVAC topology into BEM-oriented HVAC topology.

1 as building envelopes and their thermal properties. Additionally, internal partitions,
2 zones, and their connections are defined to accurately represent the spatial config-
3 uration and thermal zones of the building. The geometric BEM model can only be
4 generated from the architectural BIM model if the BIM model provides a high level of
5 detail regarding building geometry, openings, and construction, as demonstrated in
6 our previous work [16, 34]. However, due to data limitations, only a simplified BIM
7 model with space entities is accessible in this work, which cannot support the gen-
8 eration of a complete geometric model for EnergyPlus simulation. Therefore, given
9 this constraint and the research focus, a geometric BEM model in IDF format, with-
10 out active system settings, was manually created based on architectural drawings,
11 as detailed in Section 3. The HVAC topology was then used to enrich the geometric
12 BEM model with detailed HVAC information, resulting in a simulation-ready BEM
13 model for EnergyPlus simulation.

14 The HVAC topology and IDF editing processes are seamlessly integrated into a
15 single coding platform by leveraging a Python environment with RDFLib and Eppy.
16 The procedure can be outlined as follows: Each space entity is correlated with a cor-

1 responding thermal zone within the Zone class of EnergyPlus. The attributes of space
2 entities related to internal heat gains are transferred to the appropriate fields within
3 the People, Lights, and ElectricEquipment classes. Similarly, properties associated
4 with control strategies are linked to the field within the ZoneControl:Thermostat
5 class. Additional data, such as hourly schedules, are extracted from several CSV
6 files, with the properties providing only their indexing information. Moreover, there
7 are three approaches to translating HVAC-related information from the topology
8 into fields in the IDF file. The first approach involves using the classes HVACTem-
9 plate:Zone, HVACTemplate:System, and HVACTemplate:Plant to assign fields by
10 parsing the entities and in the generated HVAC topology, offering convenience and
11 error-proofing. The second approach entails introducing the class ZoneHVAC and
12 other device-level HVAC-related classes, demanding comprehensive and highly de-
13 tailed information for each HVAC component. The third approach, which can be
14 considered as the combination of them, utilizes the HVACTemplate classes to es-
15 tablish the structure for HVAC-related classes, generating an initial IDF file and
16 then refining equipment details based on properties of the obtained HVAC topol-
17 ogy. In this study, the third approach was adopted due to the complexity of the
18 HVAC system and the completeness of metadata provided by the estate team. The
19 schematic diagram illustrating the mapping from the HVAC topology to the BEM
20 model can be found in Fig. 7. Finally, the time cost and simulation results, in
21 terms of space’s indoor temperatures and energy use, are both used to validate the
22 proposed framework’s performance.

23 **3. Case study**

24 This section delves into the case study across four dimensions: providing a build-
25 ing overview, detailing data preprocessing of BIM files, defining additional parametric
26 values for building performance simulation, and describing the modelling environ-
27 ment.

Figure 7: Schematic diagram of the mapping from HVAC topology to BEM model.

1 3.1. Overview of OPS building

2 The proposed framework was implemented in a newly constructed high-rise build-
 3 ing, namely One Pool Street (OPS), situated within the UCL East Campus. OPS
 4 serves as a multi-functional building equipped with a state-of-the-art HVAC system
 5 with diverse energy technologies, which is monitored and controlled by a Building
 6 Management System (BMS). For cooling purposes, an air-cooled chiller is installed to
 7 provide chilled water for AHUs and FCUs to respond to space cooling requirements.
 8 For heating purposes, the building is connected to a district heating system to supply
 9 the heating coils in AHUs, FCUs, and Radiators. Many MVHRs exist to enhance
 10 ventilation and improve energy performance via recycling waste heat in several areas.
 11 All the aforementioned energy technologies are implemented in the podium section
 12 of this building, which is the basis where two towers (east and west) are founded.
 13 The podium has common areas from the ground floor to the second floor, as shown
 14 in Figure 8, where an Autodesk Navisworks model is displayed. The areas where
 15 the two towers are based are shown as "holes" in the top slab in this figure.

16 The west and east towers, designated for residential purposes, do not require
 17 cooling and only have radiators for heating purposes. Therefore, compared to the
 18 towers, manually constructing the building energy model for such a complex energy
 19 system in the podium area would be arduous, extremely time-consuming, and even
 20 susceptible to mistakes, which makes it an ideal scenario for assessing the effectiveness

1 of the proposed framework with a focus on HVAC information. Meanwhile, the
 2 informative HVAC topology would be highly beneficial for building management
 3 services as it effectively handles heterogeneous data.

Figure 8: 3D visualization of the OPS podium.

4 3.2. Data preprocessing

5 A simple and optimal scenario would involve inputting a single MEP-IFC file into
 6 the geometric relationship check workflow to establish the HVAC topology. However,
 7 due to the large size and complexity of the geometric data at LOD 300-400 granu-
 8 larity, there's a memory issue when running GRC as the number of pair checks for
 9 N elements grows polynomially $O(n^2)$. For N elements, the number of pair checks is
 10 $\frac{N(N-1)}{2}$ and for $N \approx 20,000$ the number of pair checks approaches 200 million pairs.
 11 Thus, it becomes necessary to partition the entire MEP-IFC file into two smaller
 12 ones: one containing air-loop domain data and one containing water-loop domain
 13 data. This approach optimally reduces the size of IFC files, minimizing the need for
 14 manual intervention. Figure 9 illustrates the raw data, comprising the ARC-BIM
 15 model (Part 1) and MEP-BIM model (Part 2) in Revit, as well as the exported IFC
 16 files from the Revit files for the proposed framework (parts A, B and C). Additionally,
 17 alongside the BIM models, schedules for lighting, occupancy, electrical equipment,
 18 and control strategies are stored in a few CSV files, facilitating indexing during the
 19 parsing of HVAC topology.

20 As shown in Figure 9, the available ARC-BIM model is relatively basic, contain-
 21 ing only space entities and lacking sufficient details on openings and construction to
 22 generate a complete geometric BEM model. Therefore, in this work, the geometric

Figure 9: 3D visualization of BIM input data and the exported IFC files for use in the BIM2BEM framework.

1 module of the IDF file was manually created using Grasshopper-Honeybee, based
 2 on the detailed design drawings. Subsequently, the initial IDF file was automati-
 3 cally enriched with comprehensive and detailed HVAC settings, using the proposed
 4 framework and the corresponding generated HVAC topology to make it ready for
 5 simulation.

6 *3.3. Additional parametric setting*

7 Due to data limitations, several parameters critical for building performance sim-
 8 ulation remain unavailable in addition to BIM data and device manuals. Specifically,
 9 detailed information on construction and electrical systems is not accessible or in-
 10 tegrated into the BIM models, resulting in missing data on the thermal properties
 11 of the building envelope and internal heat gains, which are required for performance
 12 simulation. To address this issue, building regulations most closely aligned with the
 13 construction characteristics and age of the new building were selected. This approach
 14 ensures that the building envelope parameters presented are as realistic as possible,
 15 given the current data availability. Tables 3 and 4 outline the key parameters re-
 16 quired for building performance simulation and their respective sources. Further
 17 collection of actual construction data and detailed interior design parameters could

1 facilitate updates to the existing parametric settings, thereby improving the reliabil-
 2 ity of building performance simulations. However, given the current data availability
 3 for this case study, only floor plans and a simplified ARC-BIM model are accessible,
 4 while the HVAC data is comparatively more detailed and comprehensive. As a re-
 5 sult, in this study, HVAC information is directly sourced from the actual BIM files
 6 and design manuals, while certain building-related parameters have been reasonably
 7 simplified and, where necessary, assumed.

Table 3: Parametric setting for building envelope and operation.

Domain	Item	Value	Data source
Envelope	Roof	0.18 W/(m ² K)	Building regulation [41]
	External wall	0.26 W/(m ² K)	
	Floor	0.18 W/(m ² K)	
	Window	1.6 W/(m ² K)	
Operation	Primary function rooms	21 +-1 °C for room temperature at daytime	BMS manual
	Secondary function rooms	18 °C for supply air temperature at daytime	

Table 4: Parametric setting for internal heat gains of several main spaces [42, 43]

Item	Unit	Office	Auditorium	Lobby	Lab	Toilet
Lighting	W/m ²	7.5	5	5	12.5	5
People	Person/m ²	0.11	0.34	0.12	0.10	0.11
Equipment	W/m ²	11.99	1.78	5.27	8.73	4.57

8 3.4. Modelling environment

9 The entire framework was executed on a standard laptop equipped with a 13th
 10 Gen Intel(R) Core(TM) i7 processor and 32 GB of RAM. Data preprocessing of BIM
 11 models was carried out in Revit 2018 to export the IFC files, while the BIM2BEM
 12 framework was developed within the Python environment, utilizing RDFLib for pars-
 13 ing topology and Eppy for BEM generation. Additionally, building performance
 14 simulation was performed by invoking the EnergyPlus 9.5 simulation engine.

4. Results and discussions

The proposed framework was conducted as mentioned in the above sections, and this section elaborates upon the results and discussions in three aspects, including the generated HVAC topology, framework performance, as well as limitations and future work.

4.1. Knowledge graph and HVAC topology

Although the whole MEP-IFC file and ARC-IFC file (space topology) can be imported into the geometric relationship checking workflow directly, the out-of-memory issue can not be avoided if a regular laptop is used. Thus, after the data preprocessing, three IFC files regarding space, air-loop subsystem, and water-loop subsystem were generated for geometric relation check. The conducted pair checks between terminal units/AHUs/Radiators/FCUs and spaces were approximately 115,000, which took several minutes. The conducted pair checks among the elements in the air-loop subsystem and the water-loop were approximately 38,000,000 pairs and 101,000,000 pairs, respectively. Moreover, the path-finding process based on depth-first search algorithms was implemented to establish the structure of the informative HVAC topology.

4.1.1. Geometry-induced knowledge graph

Initially, a geometry-induced knowledge graph of the HVAC system was established to directly reflect the geometric relationship among all elements in the inputted IFC files. Figure 10 provides an overview of the geometry-induced knowledge graph alongside a detailed view of a set of ducts and their digital counterparts within the graph. The graph appears non-structural because there are no discernible logical relationships among these elements. Although this graph may not be directly applicable to generating a BEM model, it offers valuable insights for directly detecting errors in the inputted IFC files using the ruleset outlined in Section 2.2.2. Figure 10 also shows some of the detected issues by human errors or extraction from the federated BIM model, which can be summarized into three types, i.e., a) abnormal clash, b) missing element, and c) geometric mismatch. Abnormal clashes typically occur

1 in areas with dense element distribution or highly complex pipeline configurations,
2 while missing elements are often found within intricate pipeline networks. Geomet-
3 ric mismatches are irregularly and subtly distributed across various areas. The error
4 detection results underscore the importance of the proposed GRC-based workflow
5 in improving BIM data quality and ensuring the completeness of the HVAC graph.
6 However, despite the accuracy of the error detection in identifying issues, manual
7 intervention for error correction—such as adding or removing links in the geometry-
8 induced knowledge graph—remains necessary.

9 Furthermore, depth-first search algorithms were employed in the path-finding
10 process to establish logical connections between air-side terminals and air-side sys-
11 tems (e.g., AHUs, MVHRs, and FCUs), as well as between water-side terminals (e.g.,
12 AHUs, radiators, and FCUs) and water pumps. These processes can also indirectly
13 detect errors and support the generation of an informative HVAC topology. If a
14 path cannot be found between a particular air terminal and an air-side system, it
15 can be inferred that there may be undetected errors that were not identified by the
16 ruleset. Similarly, if an air-side terminal entity is linked to more than one air-side
17 system, or if a pipe entity is connected to both Chilled Water (CHW) pumps and
18 Low-Temperature Hot Water (LTHW) pumps simultaneously, a double-check of the
19 corresponding BIM elements is required.

20 *4.1.2. Informative HVAC topology*

21 Figure 11 illustrates the overview of the generated informative HVAC topology
22 and several critical air-supply subsystems. In this case, there are four major air sup-
23 ply mechanisms around the building, which include: a) AHU2VAV2Diffuser2Zone, b)
24 MVHR2FCU2Diffuser2Zone, c) AHU2Diffuser2Zone, and d) MVHR2Diffuser2Zone.
25 The device performance information was stored as properties of each entity, as shown
26 in Part e) of Figure 11. Based on the informative HVAC topology, it can be inferred
27 that, among the nine AHUs, four of them are Variable Air Volume (VAV) systems
28 that supply fresh air to zones via VAV boxes, serving the general areas, such as
29 workspace, meeting rooms, and learning hubs. The remaining five are Constant Air
30 Volume (CAV) systems, which serve an auditorium, toilets, corridors, cupboards,

Figure 10: Geometry-induced HVAC knowledge graph and error detection associated with a) abnormal clash, b) element missing, and c) geometric mismatch.

1 and other ancillary areas. Additionally, six of the AHUs are linked with both the
 2 LTHW and CHW pumps for heating and cooling purposes, while three of them are
 3 not linked to the CHW pumps as they service the toilets and showers. Moreover,
 4 nine MVHR-based ventilation systems for heat recovery purposes are identified. Of
 5 these, six are in series with FCUs to serve the common rooms and teaching spaces,
 6 while the remaining three isolated systems directly serve laundry rooms and music
 7 rooms. Overall, approximately 44% of the zones are served by AHUs and 9% by
 8 MVHRs. In the other zones, only FCUs, Radiators, and door heaters are installed
 9 to meet the heating or cooling needs of spaces that do not require fresh air.

10 The generated informative HVAC topology embodies significant benefits in com-
 11 prehending HVAC systems, particularly for the complex systems in large-volume
 12 buildings, through systematically mapping out the logical connections among air-side
 13 and water-side components. Each component is documented with detailed proper-
 14 ties, ensuring access to critical information about device performance and control
 15 methods. A notable feature of the informative HVAC topology is its compatibility
 16 with query languages, allowing for efficient retrieval of specific information to trou-

1 bleshoot and facilitate decision-making. Moreover, this topology enables seamless
 2 cross-referencing and validation with schematic drawings of HVAC designs, which
 3 can not only mitigate the likelihood of errors or omissions but also facilitate in-
 4 tegration with BMS and building performance simulation. Finally, a double-check
 5 process against HVAC schematic drawings was implemented to ensure the generated
 6 topology was entirely accurate.

Figure 11: Informative HVAC topology with four air-supply subsystems (a–d) within the HVAC system, along with an example of entities’ properties (e).

7 4.1.3. BEM-oriented HVAC topology

8 Considering the feasibility and complexity of the proposed framework, a BEM-
 9 oriented HVAC topology focusing on thermal zones was established through a trans-
 10 formation process from the informative HVAC topology. With each transformation,
 11 the topology becomes less complex while gaining structural clarity. Ultimately, the
 12 BEM-oriented HVAC topology was designed to adhere to the modelling language
 13 rules of EnergyPlus. One key point is that, for each space, a single hypothetical ter-
 14 minal entity was created for each type, representing all terminal units of that type,
 15 with a capacity equal to the combined capacities of the individual units. Figure 12
 16 illustrates the entity inventories at each stage, from the input IFC files to the BEM-
 17 oriented topology. As shown, the number of entities in the BEM-oriented topology

1 is approximately 300, significantly fewer than those in both the geometry-induced
 2 knowledge graph and the informative HVAC topology.

Figure 12: Overview diagrams and entity inventories for BIM data, geometry-induced knowledge graph, informative HVAC topology, and BEM-oriented HVAC topology.

3 4.2. Framework performance

4 The proposed BIM2BEM framework aims to generate BEM models automatically,
 5 accurately and promptly. The following subsections elaborate on two critical aspects,
 6 including time cost and building performance simulation.

7 4.2.1. Time cost for BIM2BEM

8 This research endeavours to achieve automation in BIM2BEM generation, focus-
 9 ing on complex HVAC systems with as little manual intervention as possible. There
 10 are three relatively time-consuming parts within this framework, including geometric
 11 relation checking, HVAC topology generation, and building performance simulation.
 12 Regarding the geometric relation check process within the HVAC system, it took
 13 approximately 4 hours and 0.5 hours for the air-loop and water-loop IFC files, re-
 14 spectively, while the checking process between spaces and terminals required only
 15 several minutes. Hence, generating a geometry-induced HVAC graph combined with
 16 IFC parsing and geometric relation checking took nearly 5 hours, with errors also
 17 identified. Then, the manual work for fixing errors took 2 hours, which involved

1 adding and deleting the corresponding links between HVAC entities in the graph.
2 Subsequently, the establishment of the informative HVAC topology based on the
3 path-finding process and the simplification to BEM-oriented topology took approx-
4 imately 2.5 hours and half an hour, respectively. Finally, the BEM generation and
5 execution, which involved refining the IDF file and conducting a whole-year build-
6 ing performance simulation, were completed in under 20 minutes within the Python
7 environment by invoking EnergyPlus as the simulation engine. In summary, au-
8 tomatically achieving the generation of a building energy model (with only a few
9 manual interventions required to fix errors) via the proposed framework required a
10 time investment of fewer than 10 hours.

11 According to previous references [44, 45] on manual modelling times, the process
12 of modelling complex buildings with detailed HVAC configurations typically takes
13 several days or even longer. The time required for manual modelling is strongly
14 influenced by the designer’s expertise with the platform and knowledge of the build-
15 ing’s systems. The proposed framework, therefore, offers a significant reduction in
16 modelling time, bringing it down to just several hours, even when accounting for er-
17 rors in the BIM data. This underscores the framework’s efficiency and its potential
18 to support and streamline the BIM2BEM process, particularly in relation to HVAC
19 systems, while minimising the need for extensive manual intervention and the like-
20 lihood of errors. The effectiveness of the framework was demonstrated in this case
21 study involving a building with a complex HVAC system, which included over 160
22 spaces, more than 600 terminals, nearly 20 AHUs and MVHRs, and over 60 FCUs.

23 Although most stages within this framework are automated, data preparation re-
24 mains a manual task, especially when the data source format, e.g., schedule, weather,
25 and device properties, does not match the input format of the framework. Moreover,
26 a high-quality MEP-BIM model above LOD300 is essential, as lower data quality
27 may lead to errors in generating HVAC topology, such as incorrect or missing links
28 among elements. This significantly amplifies the manual effort needed to rectify
29 errors, thus reducing the efficiency of this framework.

1 4.2.2. Building performance simulation

2 This study focuses on two critical indicators, namely indoor temperature and
3 energy use, concerning the building performance simulation of the generated BEM
4 model for a newly constructed building with a total floor area of 8,800 sq.m (com-
5 prising 5,300 sq.m of conditioned area and 3,500 sq.m of unconditioned area). The
6 simulated indoor temperatures are to verify the ability of the designed HVAC system
7 to meet the heating/cooling requirements of the building, while the energy use indi-
8 cates can serve as a reference for evaluating the performance of the designed HVAC
9 system.

10 Figure 13 shows the outdoor temperature in London and the indoor temperature
11 of a few typical rooms with their No., function, and HVAC terminal type, including a
12 toilet, a lobby, a corridor, a learning hub, a corridor, and an auditorium. According
13 to the HVAC system manuals, the control strategy was set out to maintain the
14 indoor temperature of 20 ± 1 °C regarding the spaces supplied by FCUs and
15 AHUs. However, regarding toilets and other ancillary spaces, the control strategy
16 was set out to maintain a supply-air temperature of 18 ± 1 °C. Meanwhile,
17 the whole year was divided into heating, cooling, and transition seasons, while the
18 HVAC system was only in operation for the daytime. The simulation results of indoor
19 temperature can provide a clear picture to designers or managers. In parts b), c)
20 and d) of Figure 13, it can be seen that the three typical types of terminal units can
21 both maintain the indoor temperature of their respective rooms within the expected
22 range, i.e., $20 \text{ °C} - 22 \text{ °C}$ during the daytime. Thanks to the excellent thermal
23 properties of this newly constructed building, the indoor temperatures do not drop
24 below 10 °C during most of the night in winter. Moreover, regarding the toilet and
25 corridor without heating/cooling terminals, as shown in parts e) and f) of Fig. 13, the
26 indoor temperatures fluctuate significantly even though the ventilation terminals are
27 installed in the toilets. Nonetheless, since the model does not consider door-opening
28 actions, it's possible that the real indoor temperatures in unconditioned rooms might
29 outperform the simulated results. However, maintaining precise temperature control
30 in secondary function rooms/spaces is not as critical as it is in primary function
31 rooms. In this scenario, the existing HVAC design scheme successfully attains the

1 targeted temperature control range, as evidenced by the results derived from the
 2 proposed framework.

Figure 13: Whole-year outdoor temperature and indoor temperatures of several typical rooms.

3 This work introduced Energy Use Intensity (EUI) to evaluate the energy per-
 4 formance of the building and its HVAC system, whose equations can be found in
 5 Equation 1.

$$\text{EUI} = \frac{\sum_{h=1}^{8760} (\text{Load}_h^{\text{electricity, district heating}} \times 1)}{\text{Floorage}} \quad (1)$$

6 where Load indicates the time-series energy load of the building, and Floorage is the
 7 total floorage of the building, including conditioned and unconditioned areas. The
 8 number 8760 is the total number of hours in a 365-day year.

9 Based on the building energy simulation, the case study demonstrated good per-
 10 formance of the newly constructed OPS building, with an EUI (total electricity) of
 11 86.67 kWh/m²·year. Since the electricity meter became active at the beginning of
 12 this year, the electricity consumption for the first half of the year, from February
 13 2024 to August 2024, was recorded at 42.06 kWh/m²·6 months, with the full-year
 14 estimate being 84.12 kWh/m²·year. This closely aligns with the simulated results
 15 from the proposed framework. Regarding district heating, the simulated EUI is
 16 29.03 kWh/m²·year, lower than the previous academic year's heating energy bill of
 17 46.93 kWh/m²·year. This difference is due to the inclusion of domestic hot water
 18 consumption from common areas and accommodation sections outside the podium,
 19 which cannot be easily separated, as well as the fact that operational records show

1 the heating water loops were not turned off every night as planned. Consequently, the
2 comparison analysis of the two EUIs highlights the feasibility and credibility of the
3 proposed framework. With the activation of additional meters, more detailed real-
4 time data will become available, facilitating model calibration and further enhancing
5 the framework.

6 Furthermore, Figure 14 illustrates a breakdown analysis of the total electricity
7 EUI in terms of lighting, equipment, and HVAC components. It can be seen that
8 the proportion of lighting was similar to the equipment, while the proportion of the
9 HVAC system was slightly higher than the results obtained from previous engineering
10 practical experiences. This result overall aligns well with the ground truth, whereas
11 the little discrepancy arises from the operation mode being based on standard sce-
12 narios outlined in building manuals without considering the actual partial operation
13 caused by UCL's soft desk policy. Hence, if more precise schedules of occupant be-
14 haviours and system operation can be obtained, it would be possible to refine the
15 model details and achieve more accurate simulation results.

Figure 14: Breakdown analysis of the simulation results associated with EUI and its components.

1 *4.3. Limitations and future work*

2 In the proposed framework, defining HVAC topologies is a critical step that relies
3 on high-quality, precise IFC files specific to the HVAC domain. This process is further
4 supported by prior building knowledge to guide the semi-automated generation and
5 validate the resulting BEM. Additionally, supplementary data sources beyond BIM
6 are necessary to enrich the HVAC topology with quantitative information. Without
7 these, only structural information of HVAC systems can be extracted, leaving most
8 device capacity fields set to "Autosize" or based on assumptions. While the GRC-
9 based workflow can switch to bounding box clash detection when surface errors occur,
10 additional checking methods are needed to ensure the accuracy and completeness of
11 HVAC graphs. Meanwhile, this study focuses on generating non-geometric compo-
12 nents of BEM, which avoids architectural BIM geometry errors (e.g., slabs, walls,
13 and spaces) directly affecting HVAC graph generation. However, indirect impacts
14 may arise if space volumes are incorrectly defined, hindering the proper placement
15 of terminal devices. Furthermore, human errors often increase the need for manual
16 intervention to correct issues, even though the geometry-induced graph can pinpoint
17 specific problems, such as missing elements or geometric mismatches.

18 It is important to point out that the proposed framework focusing on HVAC con-
19 figuration and topology can be integrated into a comprehensive BIM2BEM workflow.
20 The geometric aspect of the BIM2BEM workflow—specifically the automatic genera-
21 tion of an IDF file containing building geometry and constructions, including second-
22 level space boundary topology—has been addressed in our earlier study [8, 16, 34].
23 By integrating these two aspects, a complete BIM2BEM workflow that encompasses
24 both passive and active components can be achieved. Future efforts could focus on
25 enhancing the framework's ability to manage varying data quality by incorporat-
26 ing quality-control methods at each stage, ensuring the reliability of the generated
27 building energy models. Simultaneously, the need for supplementary data beyond
28 BIM can be assessed to enrich the HVAC topology, providing a more accurate and
29 complete representation of the real-world system. Additionally, an effective calibra-
30 tion module addressing device performance could be developed to improve model
31 accuracy as more operational data becomes available.

5. Conclusions

This study proposed a framework focused on HVAC information within the BIM2BEM context, aiming to automate the generation of building simulation models primarily using MEP-IFC files. A geometry-induced HVAC graph was established to describe the connectivity among the HVAC elements through the geometric relation check workflow. By combining with the issue ruleset, error detection was performed to enhance data quality. The ontology and path-finding approaches were introduced to produce an informative HVAC topology that provides a comprehensive description of the HVAC system's structure and corresponding devices' properties. A BEM-oriented HVAC topology was established from the informative HVAC topology to represent HVAC-related information in alignment with the coding syntax of the building performance simulation model. Based on the implementation of a case study of a newly constructed building with a complex modern HVAC system, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- (1) The proposed framework enables automatic building performance simulation with detailed HVAC settings by integrating IFC files and other data sources, thereby approaching a level of near-complete automation.
- (2) The geometric relation check workflow, focusing on the HVAC domain, can achieve the geometry-induced knowledge graph to extract all the physical connectivity among the elements and then identify the precise positions of the errors in the inputted IFC files.
- (3) The informative HVAC topology plays a critical role in comprehensively reflecting the system's features by indicating the logical linking between spaces and terminals, as well as terminals and air-handling systems or water-side components, by storing the detailed device information as entity's properties.
- (4) When modelling a large-scale building featuring a complex HVAC system, the proposed framework can generate a detailed and reliable building simulation model by significantly reducing modelling time and minimizing the likelihood of errors, in contrast to manual modelling processes.

1 Overall, this study proposes a standard paradigm for automatic building perfor-
2 mance simulation with detailed HVAC settings from BIM data sources, which pro-
3 vides a generalizable technique for building digital twins that help designers assess
4 the energy performance of buildings and HVAC systems conveniently and accurately.
5 Furthermore, the HVAC topologies can not only facilitate automatic BEM genera-
6 tion but also carry substantial implications and benefits for building management
7 systems and operational strategies.

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